

Effect of Calcination Temperature of Magnesium Carbonate on the Properties of Magnesium Oxysulphate Cement

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The effect of calcination temperature of magnesium carbonate on the physical properties of magnesium oxide produced and magnesium oxysulphate cement prepared from calcined sample has been investigated by calcining basic magnesium carbonate at 700, 800, 850, 900, 950 and 1000°. It has been observed that the surface area of magnesium oxide, quantity of magnesium sulphate for normal consistency, compressive and transverse strengths are dependent on calcination temperature. The suitable temperature for calcination of basic magnesium carbonate for the preparation of magnesium oxysulphate cement is found to be 950°.

Magnesium oxysulphate cements find many industrial uses¹. Magnesium oxysulphate cement is prepared by the reaction of magnesium oxide obtained by calcination of magnesium carbonate with an aqueous solution of magnesium sulphate. It has very good binding properties. The compressive and transverse strengths of the cement are higher than the corresponding values of portland cement. A detailed study² by chemical and X-ray methods of the compounds formed in the system MgO—MgSO₄—H₂O has confirmed the existence of four magnesium oxysulphate phases: 5Mg(OH)₂.MgSO₄.3 or 2H₂O (5-phase); 3Mg(OH)₂.MgSO₄.8H₂O (3-phase); Mg(OH)₂.MgSO₄.5H₂O (1-phase); and Mg(OH)₂.2MgSO₄.3H₂O (1/2 phase). The stability of a particular phase is dependent on MgO reactivity, MgO : MgSO₄ mole ratio and curing temperature. The 3-phase occurs at low temperatures (30°), the 5-phase at both low and high temperatures (50—110°), the 1-phase at intermediate temperatures (80°) and high concentration of MgSO₄ solution, and the 1/2-phase at high temperatures (120°) and high concentrations.

In the present investigation, attempts have been made to study the effect of calcination temperature on the strength and other relevant properties of the magnesium oxysulphate cements using basic magnesium carbonate as the source of magnesium oxide.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of magnesium oxysulphate cements prepared by mixing magnesium oxide obtained by calcining basic magnesium carbonate at different temperatures and solutions of magnesium sulphate (AnalaR) are shown in Table 1. The amount of magnesium sulphate solution required for normal consistency of oxysulphate cement slowly increases in the calcination temperature range 850—950°.

The linear expansion values of magnesium oxysulphate cement gradually decreases even upto

calcination temperature 1000°. It is to be mentioned that the expansion is mostly associated with formation of Mg(OH)₂ during curing. The decrease in expansion values with increase in calcination temperature indicates that the tendency of magnesium oxide particles to form Mg(OH)₂ gradually decreases which may be due to agglomeration of oxide particles and this is supported by the gradual decrease of specific surface area of magnesium oxide.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF OXYSULPHATE CEMENT

Calcination temp. °C	Specific surface area m ² g ⁻¹	Volume of MgSO ₄ solution* for normal consistency cm ³ /100 g MgO	MgO/MgSO ₄ (mol) at normal consistency	Linear expansion (%)**
700	0.44	135	8.23	0.73
800	0.42	135	8.23	0.63
850	0.42	135	8.23	0.57
900	0.41	140	7.93	0.56
950	0.40	145	7.66	0.48
1000	0.40	140	7.93	0.42

*Sp. gr.=1.24. **7 days curing.

The relation of calcination temperature with the compressive and transverse strengths of cements is shown in Table 2. In most of the cases, both compressive and transverse strengths increase with the increase in calcination temperature upto 950° and then decrease. This may be due to the fact that magnesium oxide formed at 950° has a maximum reactivity to form magnesium oxysulphate phase.

From the compressive strength results it may be concluded that 950° is the most suitable temperature for calcination of magnesium carbonate and the MgO thus obtained has the highest reactivity to form magnesium oxysulphate phase almost upto completion, and hence highest compressive strength result is obtained.

TABLE 2—COMPRESSIVE AND TRANSVERSE STRENGTHS OF OXYSULPHATE CEMENTS

	Calcination temp. °C	Curing period (days)			
		3	7	14	28
Compressive strength Kgf cm ⁻²	700	62	83	91	103
	800	77	83	86	89
	850	103	110	116	121
	900	110	121	131	135
	950	124	127	135	138
	1000	77	96	103	110
Transverse strength Kgf cm ⁻²	700	11	14	20	22
	800	21	25	31	36
	850	36	37	40	41
	900	45	46	83	83
	950	62	83	86	89
	1000	38	40	41	42

Experimental

Basic magnesium carbonate (B.D.H.) was analysed following standard methods of chemical analysis, i.e. silica and mixed oxides gravimetrically, Fe₂O₃ colorimetrically, CaO and MgO complexometrically. The composition was found to be CaO, 2.8 and MgO, 46.90% with traces of SiO₂, iron oxide and Al₂O₃; loss due to ignition was 50.10%.

Fine powder of basic magnesium carbonate (B.D.H.) was calcined in refractory crucibles in an electric muffle furnace at temperatures 700, 800, 850, 900, 950 and 1000° for 3 h. The temperature was raised at a rate of 5° min⁻¹ to the required value. After calcination, the material was cooled and ground in a steel pot mill for 6 h and stored.

A solution of magnesium sulphate (sp. gr. 1.24) was prepared by dissolving the required amount of

MgSO₄·7H₂O (B.D.H.) in deionised water. Specific gravity was checked by pycnometric method. The specific surface of the oxides was measured by the air-permeability method⁵ maintaining a porosity of 0.802. The consistency of magnesium oxysulphate cements was determined by following the standard method⁶. Test pieces were prepared in 62.5 mm × 12.5 mm × 12.5 mm steel moulds following the standard method⁶ and the expansion value was measured by a travelling microscope. For measuring compressive strength, 12.5 mm cubical briquettes and for transverse strength 62.5 mm × 12.5 mm × 12.5 mm bars were prepared in steel moulds employing standard methods⁶. Compressive and transverse strengths were measured in a manually operated hydraulic press.

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